

The Private Pavillon

It dedicates an exceptional spatial arrangement which meets the requirements dictated by the intimacy of the first lady of the palace: Lalla Zineb, spouse of Ba Hmad. Indeed, it is the only pavilion completely covered, and illuminated by roof windows *shemmasiat* all around the ceiling.

It is made up of two rooms and two niches which open onto a space covered by a flat ceiling in painted cedar wood, lit and ventilated by sculpted and finely openwork plaster panels.

The ceilings of the rooms and niches, the lintels, the door and window leaves are also made of cedar wood enhanced with painted motifs and in particular stylized bouquets of flowers and bordered with epigraphic inscriptions.

Construction work on this pavilion was completed in 1898.